

Comparative Study between Long Proximal Femoral Nailing and Short Proximal Femoral Nailing For Intertrochanteric Fracture of FemurSukomal Sarkar¹, Snehasish Datta², Sankar Deb Roy³, Ijack Debbarma⁴¹MS Orthopedic, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Hospital²MS Orthopedic, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Hospital³MS Orthopedic, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Hospital⁴MS Orthopedic, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Hospital

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The primary factors contributing to the increase in proximal femoral fracture frequency are sedentary lifestyles and longer life expectancies. Intertrochanteric (IT) fractures account for around half of all fractures, and stress is the primary cause of 90% of IT fractures in the elderly due to associated osteoporosis. High-velocity trauma is the cause of IT fractures in children. Both short and long PFN are used to treat IT fractures, and each has pros and cons of its own. In the meanwhile, there has been some dispute about the length of the nail. Benefits of using a brief Proximal Femoral Nailing (PFN) have been reported, such as a shorter recovery period, less blood loss after surgery, and a consequently lower need for blood transfusions.

Aim: To evaluate long PFN and short PFN for IT fracture of femur.

Method: This randomized investigation was conducted in a tertiary hospital in Department of Orthopaedics. The patients classified as Type III and Type IV fracture patterns by Boyd & Griffin, were included in this investigation. Patients in group A underwent short PFN surgery, meeting the inclusion criteria, while patients in group B underwent long PFN surgery. For the analysis of data method of double blinding was used. Moreover, the Pearson's Chi square test was used to associate several qualitative factors.

Results: According to the analysis of current study 30% of long group patients have 3rd type of fracture along with 20% of short group. Moreover, 70% of long group patients were having 4th type of fracture and 80% of short group patients found with 4th type of fracture. The mean weight of long PFN group was 58.96 kg and short group was 65.78 kg. Moreover, the pre-operation Hb of long PFN group was 11.78 and short group was 12.54 ($p > .05$). Further, blood loss among long PFN group was 341.36 ml and short PFN group was 136.36 ml ($p < .05$). The short PFN reduction's quality was noticeably higher. Compared to 22 of the 40 instances in the long PFN, 30 out of 40 had a good decrease. Compared to the long PFN group, the intra-operative complications in the short PFN group were substantially lower.

Conclusion: It has been concluded that using short PFN is clearly superior to using long PFN in terms of mean surgery duration, C-arm time, incision length, intra-operative blood loss, intra-operative complication, postoperative complication, shorter mean time of union, and higher quality of reduction and lower extremity functionality scale scores.

Keywords: PFN, long and short PFN, stable, intra-operative.

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Introduction

The proximal femur fractures are considered as the most severe injuries. The elderly people are frequently impacted by them [1]. In addition to this, sedentary lifestyle and longer life duration are the main causes of the rise in the frequency of these proximal femoral fractures [2]. About half of all fractures are intertrochanteric, and 90% of intertrochanteric (IT) fractures in the elderly people are caused by stress because of correlated osteoporosis [3]. In youngsters, IT fractures are caused by high-velocity trauma [4].

IT fracture account for 5% of all hip fractures; of these, 35–40% are unstable fractures consisting of three or four parts, which are linked to high rates of morbidity and death. The management of unstable IT fractures in older patients is difficult and contentious because it is difficult to achieve anatomical reduction [5]. The main causes of early weight loss and the bad outcomes in these situations are osteoporosis and instability. These fractures can be successfully treated with conventional implants such as cephalo medullary nails, angular blade plates, or dynamic hip screws [6]. Percutaneous insertion and enhanced fracture fixation biomechanics are two of the

nail's hypothesised benefits [7]. A typical consequence of extramedullary devices is the medial displacement of the femoral shaft with an intramedullary device, which is produced biomechanically by a very significant force [8]. Compared to extramedullary sliding devices, the use of intramedullary devices facilitates a quicker recovery of postoperative walking ability [9].

Even if the incidences of peri-prosthetic fractures are declining with better nail designs, the risk remains the same. IT fractures are being treated using short and long PFN each of which has advantages and disadvantages of its own [10]. Regarding the nail's length, there has been some discussion in the interim [11]. Using a brief Proximal Femoral Nailing (PFN) has been noted to have its benefits including a reduced recovery period, less post-operative blood loss, and a correspondingly lower rate of transfusions of blood [12]. Therefore, the goal of this study is to come to a reliable conclusion about the usage of short vs. long PFN for the optimal management of IT fractures.

Aim: To evaluate long PFN and short PFN for IT fracture of femur.

Methods

This investigation was initiated after receiving approval from the ethical clearance committee. This randomized investigation was conducted in a

tertiary hospital in Department of Orthopaedics. The patients classified as Type III and Type IV fracture patterns by Boyd & Griffin, were included in this investigation. Patients in group A underwent short PFN surgery, meeting the inclusion criteria, while patients in group B underwent long PFN surgery. Every patient received complete information about the trial, and those who chose to participate gave their informed consent.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients above 50 years of age
- Patients with IT fracture

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with any pathological causes for fracture
- Patients aged less than 50 years
- Patients with multiple limb fracture

Analysis: For the analysis of data method of double blinding was used. Moreover, the Pearson's Chi square test was used to associate several qualitative factors.

Results

Table 1: Gender

Type	Male (%)	Female (%)
Long PFN	24 (60%)	16 (40%)
Short PFN	28 (70%)	12 (30%)

According to the outcome of table 1, there were 60% male and 40% female patients in long group. The short group involved 70% male and 30% female.

Table 2: Type of fracture

Type of fracture	Long PFN (%)	Short PFN (%)
3	12 (30%)	8 (20%)
4	28 (70%)	32 (80%)

As per the outcome of table 2, 30% of long group patients have 3rd type of fracture along with 20% of short group. Moreover, 70% of long group patients were having 4th type of fracture and 80% of short group patients found with 4th type of fracture.

Table 3: Mean weight

Type	Mean weight (Kg)
Long PFN	58.96
Short PFN	65.78

As per the table 3, the mean weight of long PFN group was 58.96 kg and short group was 65.78 kg.

Table 4: Pre operation Hb

Type	Pre operation HB	P value
Long PFN	11.78	0.067
Short PFN	12.54	

According to table 4, the pre operation HB of long PFN group was 11.78 and short group was 12.54. There was no significant association ($p > .05$).

Table 5: K wire support

Type	Percentage
Long PFN	21.6
Short PFN	18

As per the table 5, there were 21.6% patients of long PFN group had required additional K-wire support and 18% patients of short PFN group needed it.

Table 6: Mean nail diameter

Type	MM
Long PFN	11.40
Short PFN	11.91

As per the outcome of table 6, the mean nail diameter value of long PFN group was 11.40mm and short PFN was 11.91mm. There was no significant association ($p > .05$).

Table 7: Mean anti rotation screw width

Type	MM	P value
Long PFN	77.92	0.136
Short PFN	82.91	

According to table 7, the mean anti rotation screw with for long PFN was 77.92mm and short PFN was 82.91mm. There was no significant association ($p > .05$).

Table 8: Mean duration of surgery

Type	Minutes	P value
Long PFN	109.36	0.001
Short PFN	80.36	

As per the outcome of table 8, the mean duration of surgery for long PFN group was 109.36min and short PFN was 80.36 min. There was a significant association ($p < .05$). Mean duration of surgery for short PFN was significantly lower.

Table 9: Blood loss

Type	ml	P value
Long PFN	341.36	0.001
Short PFN	136.36	

According to the outcome of table 9, the level of blood loss among long PFN group was 341.36 ml and short PFN group was 136.36 ml. There was a significant association ($p < .05$). Blood loss was significantly less in short PFN.

Further, results shows that the mean angle in long PFN was 123.41 degree and short PFN was 123.56 degree. Moreover, the compression screw width in long PFN was 95.96mm and short PFN was 93.65mm. There was a no significant association ($p > .05$). In addition to this, the mean length of

incision in long PFN was 11.09cm and short PFN was 10.09cm, showing a significant association ($p < .05$).

Moreover, the mean C-arm time was 42.01 minutes for long PFN and 31.89 minutes. There was statistically significant association ($p < .05$). In addition to this, the quality of reduction was significantly better in short PFN 28 out of 40 and long PFN was 26 out of 40. Apart from this, the analysis has found statistically significant association for pre-intra-operative complication in the short PFN as it was lesser than long PFN group. The post intra-operative

complication was also lesser for short PFN compare to long PFN. Moreover, the mean time of union in short PFN was 10.1 weeks and long PFN was 20.10 weeks, ($p < .05$). Lastly, it is found that the mean value of extremity functionality for short PFN was 62.36 and long PFN was 67.01, ($p > .05$).

Discussion

The medial displacement of the femoral shaft with an intramedullary device, which is generated biomechanically by a very large force, is a common side effect of extramedullary implants. When intramedullary devices are used, postoperative walking ability can recover more quickly than with extramedullary sliding devices. According to the analysis of data of current study, 30% of long group patients have 3rd type of fracture along with 20% of short group. Moreover, 70% of long group patients were having 4th type of fracture and 80% of short group patients found with 4th type of fracture. The mean weight of long PFN group was 58.96 kg and short group was 65.78 kg. Moreover, the pre-operation Hb of long PFN group was 11.78 and short group was 12.54 ($p > .05$). According to Mahesh Kumar, Mahesh and Kumar, (2017) [13], the average weight in the long PFN group was 57.68 kg, while the short PFN group was 65.18 kg. The pre-operative hemoglobin mean was 12.557 for short PFN and 11.71 for long PFN ($p = .0683$). There were 38 cases in short PFN and 36 cases in long PFN that had closed reduction.

As per the analysis of current study, 21.6% patients of long PFN group had required additional K-wire support and 18% patients of short PFN group needed it. The mean nail diameter value of long PFN group was 11.40mm and short PFN was 11.91mm. Additionally, the mean anti rotation screw with for long PFN was 77.92mm and short PFN was 82.91mm ($p > .05$). The study of Prakashappa (2021) [14] has found that extra assistance was needed for 17% in the short PFN group and 22.5% in the long PFN group required K wires. The mean angle is 133.65 degrees for short PFN and -133.75 degrees for long PFN. Long PFN = 10.44 mm, short PFN = 10.95 mm is the mean nail diameter. The anti-rotation screw widths are 81.10 mm for short PFN and 78.50 mm for long PFN ($p = .12$). Compression screw widths are -96.75 mm for long PFNs and -94.38 mm for short PFN groups ($p = .1289$).

Moreover, the outcome of current study has suggested that the level of blood loss among long PFN group was 341.36 ml and short PFN group was 136.36 ml ($p < .05$). The short PFN reduction's quality was noticeably higher. Compared to 22 of the 40 instances in the long PFN, 30 out of 40 had a good decrease. Compared to the long PFN group, the intra-operative complications in the short PFN group were substantially lower. The short PFN group experienced significantly fewer post-operative

complications than the long PFN group [15]. Moreover, current study has found that, the quality of reduction was significantly better in short PFN 28 out of 40 and long PFN was 26 out of 40. Apart from this, the analysis has found significantly statistical association for pre intra-operative complication in the short PFN as it was lesser than long PFN group. The post intra-operative complication was also lesser for short PFN compare to long PFN. Moreover, the mean time of union in short PFN was 10.1 weeks and long PFN was 20.10 weeks ($p < .05$).

Moreover, the compression screw width in long PFN was 95.96mm and short PFN was 93.65mm ($p > .05$). In addition to this, the mean length of incision in long PFN was 11.09cm and short PFN was 10.09cm ($p < .05$).

Conclusion

By considering the findings of current study it has been concluded that using short PFN is clearly superior to using long PFN in terms of mean surgery duration, C-arm time, incision length, intra-operative blood loss, intra-operative complication, postoperative complication, shorter mean time of union, and higher quality of reduction and lower extremity functionality scale scores.

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